

NFDI as a Learning System

Results and Lessons Learned from the Evaluation of Base4NFDI

Franziska Fritzsche¹ <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9816-4796>, and
Dominik Obeth² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3827-9815>, Niko Wilke²

¹ GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, Germany

² Technopolis Group, Germany

³ Technopolis Group, Belgium

*Correspondence: Franziska Fritzsche, Franziska.Fritzsche@gesis.org

Abstract

Infrastructure projects are often complex structures involving multiple stakeholders, building on existing structures as well as innovating around them. Therefore, it is essential to adapt these structures to the needs of the community in order to ensure their effectiveness. But how to identify these needs? One possible solution is to carry out an external evaluation - as in the case of Base4NFDI [1].

This contribution presents data from the Technopolis Group's evaluation of Base4NFDI, the joint initiative of all consortia in NFDI [2] to develop and establish basic services for RDM. Therefore, the Base4NFDI Office and Technopolis would like to present the process and results of the evaluation in a joint presentation. The goal of the evaluation is to assess the progress and outcomes of that initiative thus far, as well as to identify areas for improvement, ensuring that the infrastructure continues to effectively support the research community.

Base4NFDI has opted for this unique and open approach to involve the NFDI community and beyond in its organizational development. Its framework is organized in a multi-phased process with a large number of stakeholders involved: Proposals for Basic Services must come from community processes within NFDI Sections [3] which develop cross-cutting solutions relevant for the domains of multiple NFDI consortia. These proposals are evaluated by a technical expert committee. After a successful submission, Base4NFDI assists these projects, offers value adding services (like training assistance), administers the funding, and monitors the process.

In view of the complexity of the project, but also the novelty of its framework, in its project proposal [4] Base4NFDI has committed to an external evaluation of its decision-making and work processes after two years. This comprehensive evaluation will form the basis for recommendations for adapting and correcting these processes. After a public tender procedure [5], the Technopolis Group [6] has been commissioned to carry out the evaluation of Base4NFDI in the period from December 2024 to August 2025.

The concept [7] is set to explore three aspects: the efficiency of the project structure and internal organisation, the relevance and coherence of the process for developing a Basic Service and the relevance of the project for the NFDI community.

Based on the project proposal and the experience gained during the project so far, the following points are of particular interest for the evaluation:

- Assessment of cooperation and support between Base4NFDI and stakeholders
- Analysis of process and resource management
- Review of the work program and task distribution
- Analysis of the submission and evaluation process for Basic Services

This is an ongoing project, results are expected by June/July 2025. Dialogue and transparency are indicators of good scientific work. As the outcome of the evaluation is based on feedback from the community, we want to present not only the results, but also suggestions for improving Base4NFDI's processes. We also like to openly share the lessons we have learned from evaluating a complex infrastructure context. This aims to demonstrate that NFDI is a dynamic and adaptive system.

Keywords: NFDI, Research Data Infrastructures, Evaluation

Resources

Evaluation methods: This evaluation employs a mixed method approach. Besides analyzing project relevant documents and data, an interview program with a broad range of actors and stakeholders of Base4NFDI is conducted, including members of the Base4NFDI task areas, principal investigators of the developer teams, representatives of NFDI sections and consortia and stakeholders involved in the strategic governance of Base4NFDI. Furthermore, two online surveys are conducted with the developer teams of Base4NFDI basic services and with individuals affiliated to NFDI member organizations which are active in the NFDI consortia. Based on the results of these data collection methods, needs for a more in-depth investigation are identified. These needs are addressed through additional interviews and focus groups on relevant topics. The process concludes with two validation workshops involving members of Base4NFDI.

Author contributions

Please include a statement on authors' contributions according to the [CreDIT guidelines](#) here. CRedit (Contributor Roles Taxonomy)'s intention is to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Franziska Fritzsche: Conceptualisation, supervision, writing

Jan Biela: Conceptualisation, methodology, investigation, validation, writing

Dominik Obeth: Conceptualisation, methodology, investigation, data curation, validation, visualization, writing

Patricia Scheiber, Lennart Stoy, Niko Wilke: investigation, data curation, validation, writing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

Base4NFDI is funded by DFG as part of NFDI. Grant Numbers: 521453681, 521460392, 521462155, 521463400, 521466146, 521471126, 521473512, 521474032, 521475185, 521476232.

Acknowledgement

If you want to acknowledge persons or institutions you can do so here.

References

- [1] "Evaluation of Base4NFDI." Base4NFDI Website. <https://base4nfdi.de/about/evaluation-of-base4nfdi> (19.03.2025)
- [2] "Consortia & Base4NFDI." NFDI Website. <https://www.nfdi.de/consortia/?lang=en> (20.03.2025)
- [3] "Sections." NFDI Website. <https://www.nfdi.de/sections/?lang=en> (20.03.2025)
- [4] L. Bernard, „Base4NFDI - Basic Services for NFDI“. Zenodo, Dez. 01, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245518>.
- [5] Terms of Reference, uploaded on "Evaluation of Base4NFDI." Base4NFDI Website. https://base4nfdi.de/images/ToR_Base4NFDI_Evaluation_Tender.pdf (02.04.2025)
- [6] Technopolis Group Website. <https://technopolis-group.com/de/> (19.03.2025)
- [7] D. Obeth, J. Biela, P. Scheiber, L. Stoy und N. Wilke, „Evaluation of Base4NFDI: Inception Report“. Zenodo, Apr. 01, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15120306>.